

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND
INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL

REPORT

2008–2009

DIRECTORS, JULY 1, 2008–JUNE 30, 2009

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* Term ended November 2008

THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

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Bowdoin College
Brigham Young University
Brill
Brown University Library
Bryn Mawr College Libraries
Bucknell University
California Digital Library
California Institute of Technology
California Lutheran University
California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo
California State University Bakersfield
California State University California Maritime Academy
California State University Channel Islands
California State University Chico
California State University Dominguez Hills
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California State University Sonoma State University
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Carleton College
Carnegie Library of Pittsburgh
Case Western Reserve University
The Catholic University of America
The Claremont Colleges
The Clark Art Institute
Coalition for Networked Information
Colby College
Colgate University
College of Charleston
College of St. Benedict/St. John's University
College of Wooster Libraries
Colorado College
Colorado State University
Columbia University
Connecticut College
Cornell University Libraries
Dartmouth College
Davidson College
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DePauw University
Dickinson College Library
Drexel University
Duke University
Earlham College
Emory University
Franklin & Marshall College
The George Washington University
Georgetown University
Georgia State University
Georgia Tech
Gettysburg College
Goucher College
Grinnell College
Gustavus Adolphus College
Hamilton College
Harvard University
Haverford College
Hope College
Indiana University
Iowa State University
Jacobs University (Bremen)
Johns Hopkins University Libraries
JSTOR
Kalamazoo College
Kenyon College
Lafayette College
Lake Forest College
Laval University Library
Lehigh University
Library and Archives Canada
Library of Congress
Linda Hall Library of Science, Engineering & Technology
Linfield College
Luther College
Macalester College Library
Manhattan College
Marquette University
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
McMaster University
Mercer University
Miami University
Michigan State University
Middlebury College
Mississippi State University Libraries
Mitchell College
Mount Holyoke College
National Agricultural Library
National Library of Medicine
The New York Public Library
New York University
North Carolina State University Libraries
Northern State University
Northeastern University
Northwestern University Libraries
Oberlin College Library
Occidental College
The Ohio State University
Ohio Wesleyan University
Oregon State University Libraries
Pacific Lutheran University
Pennsylvania State University
Pepperdine University
Preservation Technologies
Princeton University Library
Purdue University Library
Reed College
Rhodes College
Rice University
Rutgers, the state university of New Jersey
Saint Lawrence University
Sarah Lawrence College
Sewanee: The University of the South
Simmons College
Skidmore College
Smith College
Smithsonian Institution
Southeastern Library Network, Inc.
Southern Illinois University Library
Southern Methodist University
Stanford University
State University of New York at Albany
State University of New York at Brockport
State University of New York at Buffalo
State University of New York at Stony Brook
Swarthmore College
Syracuse University

Temple University Library	University of Hawaii at Manoa	University of Southern California
Texas A&M University Libraries	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	University of St. Thomas
Texas Tech University	University of Illinois, Chicago	University of Tennessee
Towson University	University of Iowa Libraries	University of Texas at Arlington
Trinity College Library	University of Kansas	University of Texas at Austin
Trinity University	University of Kentucky Libraries	University of Toronto Library
Tulane University	University of Louisville Libraries	University of Utah
Union College	University of Maryland at College Park	University of Virginia
Université de Montréal	University of Mary Washington	University of Washington
The University of Alabama Libraries	University of Massachusetts Libraries	University of Wisconsin-Madison
University of Alberta	University of Miami	University of Wyoming
University of Arizona Library	University of Michigan	U.S. Naval Academy
University of Arkansas	University of Minnesota Libraries	Vanderbilt University
University of British Columbia	University of Missouri Library	Vassar College Libraries
University of California, Berkeley	University of Montana	Villanova University
University of California, Irvine	University of Nebraska-Lincoln	Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
University of California, Los Angeles	University of Nevada, Las Vegas	Wabash College
University of California, San Diego Libraries	University of New Mexico	Washington and Lee University Library
University of California, Santa Barbara	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	Washington University Libraries
University of Chicago Library	University of Notre Dame	Wellesley College
University of Cincinnati	University of Oregon	Wesleyan University
University of Colorado at Boulder	University of Pennsylvania	Wheaton College
University of Connecticut	University of Pittsburgh	Whitman College
University of Delaware Library	University of Richmond	Williams College Libraries
University of Denver	University of Rochester	Yale University
University of Florida Libraries	University of San Francisco	
University of Georgia Libraries	University of South Carolina	
	University of South Florida	

Foundation, Corporate, and Institutional Support

(as of June 30, 2009)

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	Howard and Mathilde Rovelstad	National Endowment for the Humanities
Cummins-Allison Corporation	Institute for Library and Information	Robert W. Woodruff Foundation
Documentation Abstracts, Inc.	Services	Samuel H. Kress Foundation
EDUCAUSE	Library of Congress	

STAFF

(AS OF JUNE 30, 2009)

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DONALD PITCOCK
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JESSICA WADE
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CLIR SENIOR PRESIDENTIAL FELLOWS

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LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Stephen Nichols
Chairman of the Board

As a medievalist, I come to CLIR's chair with a keen appreciation for the staff of libraries and archives who have made my research, and that of previous generations, possible. As a digital humanist, I realize just how much my interaction with these colleagues has changed in the span of a few years.

A decade ago, there was a chasm between scholarly users and library providers. As digital literacy took hold, this gap narrowed. Today's scholars who use large-scale data sources rarely work alone. Digital research depends on collaboration at many levels: between scholars and information technology professionals; among scholars of the same and other disciplines; between scholars and students; and between scholars and the librarians and archivists who both facilitate research access and keep scholarship accessible. But this collaboration has not come easily as many continue to operate, consciously or not, in the mode of analog research.

Data-driven research requires us to understand and accept a new social, intellectual, and institutional context. Promoting this understanding and exploring new models of scholarship are at the heart of CLIR's work, as is shown in the pages of this annual report. Initiatives in cyberinfrastructure, the next scholar, and leadership are but a few of the diverse facets of this work. In all these areas, CLIR continues to provide a vital forum for tackling problems that are difficult for individual professional communities to address.

I am pleased to chair an organization that is facing these urgent challenges head on, and I look forward to the year ahead.

Stephen Nichols
November 2009

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

For years, CLIR has focused on how to reconceive information services in higher education in ways that respond to the pervasive, often turbulent changes that new technologies entail. At a time of daunting fiscal constraints and challenges, there is a growing urgency—and opportunity—to implement fundamental changes across the academy that will position our constituents to function more efficiently in the new environment for higher education in the 21st century.

Over the past year, we have combined some of our traditional programs with new areas of exploration involving a rigorous analysis of phenomena and circumstances governing academic libraries, information technology, advanced scholarship, and research. We could not have accomplished this without several new and important grants and the robust support of our sponsors. All of our work is collaborative in its general meaning, but I want to highlight two developments in particular: the emergence of a project for “deep collaboration” that could redefine the concept of the research library, and the reintegration of the Digital Library Federation (DLF) into CLIR.

Traditionally, *collaboration* has meant informal arrangements among institutions to coordinate various services and to align program investments in a way that offsets costs and avoids redundancy. Formal collaboration is evidenced in the proliferation of subscription consortia and of document-delivery and other programs that use institutional content while keeping traditional organizational structures, staffing assignments, and budgets intact. In part as a response to the dire economic conditions, these arrangements have become more experimental and entrepreneurial: they now entail not only coordination but also, more interestingly, genuine dependencies.

This summer, CLIR received a grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to work with New York University, Columbia University, the HathiTrust, and OCLC/Research Libraries Group to explore models for creating combined large-scale virtual and print repositories as surrogates for on-site printed collections held by an academic library. Research is under way to identify the policies, procedures, logistics, and infrastructure needed for print and digital repositories to make their services more widely available to university libraries and for libraries to make more effective use of those repositories in managing their own collections.

The results of this project—templates of activity, research questions, cost analyses, and a general methodological approach—should be applicable to, and replicable by, many libraries. Over time, they should produce a considerable savings of costs. If widely adopted, they will significantly redefine the physical plan of libraries, the concept of ownership, and the nature of collection development. They are persuasive examples of the potential benefits of deep collaboration.

The reintegration of DLF into CLIR presents new opportunities for providing strategic directions for both organizations' constituencies. While the reintegration requires a thoughtful period of reflection to determine the focus of its next iteration, some salient program elements are already under way. Grafting CLIR's research capabilities onto DLF, resulting in a more structured, ongoing description and assessment of the digital environment in higher education, will provide value to our sponsors. Investment in the DLF Forum will continue, emphasizing new and emerging technologies, identifying potential collaborative partners for research and development that should result in greater efficiencies, and continuing to promote standards and best practices. One important conceptual focus for DLF will be to inculcate an understanding among its sponsors and other institutions that all of the projects and programs currently under way need to be understood and managed as a national digital library environment that requires a working knowledge of its component parts and a digital architecture that unifies these various assets and tools for greater intellectual productivity.

Greater collaboration between university presses and scholarly research programs and academic societies augur for cost-effective, timely, and rigorously reviewed publications that may appear in a variety of new and unexpected formats; when aggregated they will also constitute an important element of a national scholarly ecology. DLF will expand its reach and influence, encouraging corporations to partner with colleges and universities when planning and designing projects of value to higher education. Exploring opportunities for collaborative work between universities and CLIR's emerging program to investigate nonclassified tools used by the intelligence-gathering community is another new service DLF will offer its sponsors. These efforts, taken together, represent an extraordinary platform for instantiating an interoperable, flexibly architected digital library of unprecedented depth and reach.

CLIR continues to expand its community of partners. A major grant from the Institute for Museum and Library Services is funding a programmatic alliance with the Council of Independent Colleges, working with the Appalachian College Association and United Negro College Fund, to develop workshops for future leaders in the library field. We have strengthened ties with the Center for Research Libraries through an appointment to its board, have engaged programmatically with the National Information Standards Organization, and serve as an adviser to Tan Tao University in Vietnam, a new institution that is testing many assumptions and traditions of higher education.

CLIR has remained vibrant and productive during this year of economic turmoil. The year ahead looks to be just as promising. I look forward to working with you as we manage together this era of challenge and opportunity.

Charles Henry
November 2009

THE PROGRAMS

July 1, 2008–June 30, 2009

In August 2008, CLIR published *No Brief Candle: Reconceiving Research Libraries for the 21st Century*. The report's prologue notes that "the future of the research library cannot be considered apart from the future of the academy as a whole. Trends that will influence this future are already evident; foremost among them are a distinct rise in cross-disciplinary research in the humanities as well as in the sciences, and a concomitant increase in research that involves scholars as well as graduate students and undergraduates."

CLIR's programmatic work reflects the emergence of interdisciplinarity at several levels, including the adoption of research methodologies from diverse domains of knowledge and professional interdisciplinarity, in the form of bringing together the perspectives of librarians, information technologists, administrators, and, most important, scholars themselves, in collaboration on issues of common concern.

In 2007 CLIR identified six aspects of work that would guide its agenda:

- *Cyberinfrastructure*: defining the base technologies of computation and communication, the software programs, and the data curation and preservation programs that are national in scale and requisite for the management of very large-scale multimedia data sets, especially pertaining to the digital record of our cultural heritage;
- *The Next Scholar*: exploring and assessing new methodologies, emerging fields of inquiry, intellectual strategies involving data gathering and collaboration, and modes of communication, including sharing of research data and publishing models, that are likely to define the next generation of scholars;
- *Preservation*: examining sustainable strategies for preserving all media, analog and traditional, and heightening public awareness of the risks of failing to plan for preservation;
- *The Emerging Library*: exploring the increasingly swift evolution of the concept of the library with particular focus on its core functions and the possible consequences of rapid change for library staffing, research and teaching, and economic modeling;
- *Leadership*: investigating and defining the skills and expertise needed

- to best administer, inspire, and inform the next generation; and
- *New Models*: extrapolating from an array of CLIR’s findings and other related research how academic organizations, institutions, behaviors, and culture may evolve.

This report of CLIR activities for 2008–2009 is presented according to these categories.

CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE

Try, Use, Fail, Learn (TrUFL)

TrUFL is an initiative that seeks to promote digital scholarship through advanced computing. It embraces a series of projects and activities directed toward four principal objectives: foster collaborations; provide access to resources (including data, tools, capacities, and funding); support education and training; and enhance communication. By June 30, 2009, CLIR had completed two activities within the TrUFL framework: helping to support a conference on the proposed Scaife Digital Library, a resource for graduate and undergraduate research in classics; and hosting a conference entitled “Languages Other Than Your Own,” which addressed machine-augmented access to multilingual corpora with particular reference to Arabic. The latter conference was undertaken in partnership with Tufts University and with support from the U.S. Department of Education. More information is available at <http://www.clir.org/activities/details/language.html>. A third TrUFL project, A Distant Symmetry, an 18-month effort to identify and evaluate nonclassified tools developed in the intelligence community that might be useful to humanities scholars, has been funded but not yet launched.

Promoting Digital Scholarship: Formulating Research Challenges in the Humanities, Social Sciences, and Computation

In September 2008, CLIR, in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities, convened a one-day symposium at which scholars across the humanities, social sciences, and computer sciences considered the role of research questions in promoting new scholarship. White papers commissioned for the symposium framed the discussions. A report of the meeting was published in March 2009 under the title *Working Together or Apart: Promoting the Next Generation of Digital Scholarship*. It is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub145abst.html>.

Analysis of the Effects of Mass Digitization on Scholarship

With funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and in partnership with Georgetown University, CLIR continued work on a project to assess the utility to scholars of several large-scale digitization projects. The project began with a focus on Google Book Search, Microsoft’s (now-defunct)

Live Search Books, the ACLS Humanities E-Book project, Internet Archive's text search, and the antecedent Project Gutenberg as the main sources for analysis of digitized content. CLIR commissioned four scholars from historical and literary areas of study to summarize key methodological considerations in conducting research in their respective disciplines and to assess each digitization project under scrutiny. In September, CLIR convened a meeting of scholars to discuss the commissioned research and determine next steps. CLIR will issue a public report early in 2010.

THE NEXT SCHOLAR

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries

Now in its sixth year, the CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship Program is preparing a new generation of librarians and scholars for work at the intersections of scholarship, teaching, and librarianship in the emerging research environment.

CLIR postdoctoral fellows work on projects that exploit current information technology to forge, renovate, and strengthen connections between academic library collections and their users. The program offers scholars the chance to develop new research models, collaborate with information specialists, and explore new career opportunities. Host libraries benefit from the expertise of accomplished humanists and social scientists who invigorate approaches to collection use and teaching, contribute field-specific knowledge, and provide insight into the future of scholarship. Fellows have consulted on integrating library materials and resources into the classroom, designed and implemented metadata standards, curated exhibitions in libraries and museums, organized conferences and colloquia, taught courses, written successful grant proposals for host institutions, managed archives, created Web portals, and more.

2009–10 Fellows in Academic Libraries

<i>Fellow</i>	<i>Host Institution</i>
Anne Bruder	Bryn Mawr College
Gloria Chacon	University of California, Los Angeles
Daniel Chamberlain	Occidental College
Melissa Grafe	Lehigh University
Timothy F. Jackson	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Lori Jahnke	The College of Physicians of Philadelphia
Noah Shenker	McMaster University
Heather Waldroup	Claremont University Consortium

2009–10 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Daniel Berger , University of Pennsylvania
Lydia Brandt , University of Virginia
Jun Hee Cho , Columbia University
Martin Gutmann , Syracuse University
Robert Herr , University of Massachusetts, Amherst
Kristine Hess , University of Chicago
Nicholas Johnson , The Ohio State University
Erin Lambert , University of Wisconsin-Madison
Pedro Monaville , University of Michigan
Lindsay Moore , George Washington University
Virginia Myhaver , Boston University
Daphna Oren-Magidor , Brown University
Jamie Rosenthal , University of California, San Diego
Danielle Terrazas Williams , Duke University
Jaime Wadowiec , Binghamton University
Kimberly Welch , University of Maryland, College Park

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

In 2009, 16 graduate students were selected to receive Mellon Dissertation Fellowships. The fellowships, now in their ninth year, are intended to help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue original-source doctoral research and gain skill and creativity in using primary source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories. The fellowships carry stipends of up to \$25,000 each to support dissertation research for periods of up to 12 months.

To date, the program has supported 97 graduate students who have carried out their dissertation research in a variety of public and private libraries and archives.

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives

In November 2008, CLIR made the first round of awards in its Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program. Fifteen projects nationwide received a total of \$4 million. Created in 2008 with funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the program supports the identification and cataloging of special collections and archives of high scholarly value that are difficult or impossible to locate. Award recipients create descriptive information for their hidden collections that will eventually be linked to and interoperable with all other projects funded by this grant program. In January 2009, CLIR published *Archival Management Software: A Report for the Council on Library and Information Resources*. Author Lisa Spiro describes and analyzes some of the major technologies that are available to librarians, curators, and archivists and the implications of deploying these systems for existing workflows. The report is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/spiro2009.html>.

2009–2010 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

Avery Research Center for African American History and Culture at the College of Charleston

Providing Access to African American Collections at the Avery Research Center

California Historical Society
California Ephemera Project

Center for the History of Medicine, Countway Library, Harvard Medical School

Foundations of Public Health Policy

Getty Research Institute

Uncovering Archives and Rare Photographs: Two Models for Creating Accession-level Finding Aids Using Archivists' Toolkit

Goucher College

Mapping Special Collections for Research and Teaching at Goucher College

Library of Congress

Library of Congress Multi-Sheet Map Series Collection: Africa

Litchfield Historical Society

Litchfield Historical Society's Revolutionary Era and Early Republic Holdings

New York University

The Records of the Communist Party, USA: A Preservation and Access Project

Northwestern University Library

The Africana Posters: Hidden Collections of Northwestern and Michigan State University Libraries

University and Jepson Herbaria, University of California, Berkeley

Cataloging Hidden Archives of Western Botany and Beyond

University of Michigan Library

Collaboration in Cataloging: Islamic Manuscripts at Michigan

University of Pennsylvania Libraries

Hidden Collections in the Philadelphia Area: A Consortial Processing and Cataloging Initiative

Collaborative project:

Emory University

Archives from Atlanta, Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement: The Papers of Andrew Young, SCLC, and NAACP-Atlanta Chapter

Robert W. Woodruff Library, Atlanta University Center

Processing Voter Education Project Collection

Amistad Research Center

Working for Freedom: Documenting Civil Rights Organizations

Scholarly Communication Institute

CLIR continues to serve on the planning committee for the Scholarly Communication Institute (SCI), which in 2009 focused on spatial technologies and methodologies. The SCI began in 2003 with the goal of providing an opportunity for scholars and leaders in scholarly disciplines and societies, academic libraries, information technology, and higher education administration to design, test, and implement strategies that advance the humanities through the use of innovative technologies. Since 2006, the University of Virginia has hosted SCI, which is now under the direction of Abby Smith-Rumsey. Information about the SCI is available at <http://www.uvasci.org/>.

EthicShare

In November 2008, CLIR hosted a seminar, organized by EthicShare, to identify the challenges associated with building online communities for scholars and to determine whether extensible models exist that could meet the research and collaboration needs of interdisciplinary communities. A summary of the meeting is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/issues/issues67.html#eth>.

EthicShare explores novel approaches to facilitating scholarship by taking advantage of social technologies and the expertise of the research communities it serves. EthicShare is developing a research Web site for the practical ethics community that incorporates a database of source materials and tools to enable community interaction and engagement. The interdisciplinary, multi-institutional project, currently in a pilot stage, addresses three of the major challenges researchers face in the 21st century: the overwhelming amount of information available and the difficulty of keeping up with a field; the need to master new areas of research for interdisciplinary projects; and the necessity of working collaboratively.

The project is based at the University of Minnesota and funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation with additional support from CLIR. More information about EthicShare is available at www.ethicshare.org.

PRESERVATION

Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access

CLIR, along with the Library of Congress, the National Archives and Records Administration, and the Joint Information Systems Committee of the United Kingdom, is an institutional participant in the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access. The task force was created in 2007 to identify sustainable economic models for providing access to the ever-growing amount of digital information in

the public interest. Funded by the National Science Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the task force is cochaired by Fran Berman, director of the San Diego Supercomputer Center at the University of California, San Diego, and Brian Lavoie, research scientist and economist in OCLC's Office of Research. The task force's 17 members represent a cross-section of fields and disciplines, including information and computer sciences, economics, entertainment, library and archival sciences, government, and business.

The task force's first-year report, issued in December 2008, is available at http://brtf.sdsc.edu/biblio/BRTF_Interim_Report.pdf. The group will issue its final report in late 2009. The document will propose recommendations for sustainable economic models to support access to and preservation of digital data in the public interest.

Preserving Recorded-Sound Heritage

Since 2004, CLIR has conducted work under contract with the Library of Congress (LC) and the National Recording Preservation Board in support of an ongoing study of the state of recorded-sound preservation and restoration. Recent reports have focused on copyright, with an aim to giving libraries and archives practical information on preservation and access rights, while also highlighting issues that need to be addressed at the national policy level. In March 2009, CLIR and LC copublished *Copyright and Related Issues Relevant to Digital Preservation and Dissemination of Unpublished Pre-1972 Sound Recordings by Libraries and Archives*, by June M. Besek. In September 2009, CLIR and LC copublished *Protection for Pre-1972 Sound Recordings under State Law and its Impact on Use by Nonprofit Institutions: A 10-State Analysis*, prepared by the Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property, Washington College of Law, American University, under the supervision of Peter Jaszi with the assistance of Nick Lewis.

National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program

CLIR has continued to work with the Library of Congress's National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program (NDIIPP), assisting with the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access and with the preparation of NDIIPP's final report to the U.S. Congress. NDIIPP provided funding for an intern with a background in economics and information to work with the task force. The intern, Lori Eakin, a doctoral candidate at the School of Information and Library Science at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, made a substantial contribution to the interim report as well as to the economic modeling work that took place in the spring of 2009. CLIR's publication support for NDIIPP's final report to Congress began in the late spring 2009 and is expected to continue through December 2009.

THE EMERGING LIBRARY

Faculty Research Behavior Workshops

In 2007, CLIR began offering faculty research behavior workshops, which teach library and information technology professionals ethnographic techniques that enable them to understand faculty members' work practices and how library and information services can address faculty needs. Led by Nancy Foster, an anthropologist at the University of Rochester, the workshops have been well received, with a waiting list that continues to grow. To date, CLIR has offered workshops at Wesleyan University, Kenyon College, Cornell University, the University of California at Berkeley, George Washington University, the University of Rochester, New York University, and the University of Miami.

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR facilitates a semiannual forum at which chief information officers (CIOs) of merged library and computing units in liberal arts colleges discuss issues affecting teaching and learning on their campuses. The CIOs' March 2009 meeting focused on results from MISO (Merged Information Services Organizations), a Web-based quantitative survey that measures how students, faculty, and staff use and evaluate the services and resources of colleges and universities with merged library and computing units. The CIOs have also explored strategic and tactical issues concerning cloud computing, specifically the services that have moved to the cloud and the impediments to moving more services there. In addition, members shared information about their information technology governance structures and trends in the use of technology in teaching.

LEADERSHIP

Leadership Through New Communities of Knowledge

In June 2009, CLIR received funding from the Institute of Museum and Library Services to collaborate with the Council of Independent Colleges in launching a three-year program, "Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge." The program will offer an array of professional development opportunities for library staff at small and midsize private colleges and universities. Program activities include convening workshops to help librarians strengthen leadership skills and enabling staff from less affluent institutions to experience work environments at other types of institutions, such as those affiliated with the Oberlin Group of libraries. In addition, the program will identify new topics for workshops to meet particular needs of library staff at small liberal arts colleges. The program will emphasize liberal arts colleges that are not well connected to the mainstream of American librarianship, including those that are members of the American International Consortium of Academic Libraries.

CLIR CIOs Members (as of 6/30/09)

Christopher Barth, Luther College
 Param Bedi, Bucknell University
 Theresa Byrd, Ohio Wesleyan University
 Gai Carpenter, Hampshire College
 Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
 Jose Dieudonne, Arcadia University
 Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
 Charling Chang Fagan, Sarah Lawrence College
 Carol Falcione, Barnard College
 Cathy Fennell, Rosemont College
 Chris Ferguson, Pacific Lutheran University
 Megan Fitch, Beloit College
 Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
 Perry Hanson, Brandeis University
 W. Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
 Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
 Thomas Kirk, Earlham College
 Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
 Renee Jadushlever, Mills College
 Micheline Jedrey, Wellesley College
 Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
 Felice Maciejewski, Saint Norbert College
 Neil McElroy, Lafayette College
 Pamela McQuesten, Occidental College
 Terry Metz, Wheaton College
 Kathryn Monday, University of Richmond
 Pattie Orr, Baylor University
 Charlotte Slocum Patriquin, Mount Holyoke College
 Rick Provine, DePauw University
 Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
 Suzanne Risley, Mitchell College
 Mike Roy, Middlebury College
 Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
 Elliott Shore, Bryn Mawr College
 Carol Smith, DePauw University
 Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
 Gene Wiemers, Bates College
 Frank Wojcik, SUNY College at Brockport

Frye Institute Participants Class of 2009

Frankie Baker, Cincinnati State Technical and Community College

Brooke Banks, California State University, Chico

Fred Barnhart, Loyola University Chicago

Shandon Bates, Western Carolina University

Marisa Benson, Emory University

Ellen Yu Borkowski, University of Maryland

Chris Bourg, Stanford University

Susanna Boylston, Davidson College

Sandra Bracegirdle, The John Rylands University Library

Jody Britten, Butler University

Darlene Brooks, Rhodes College

Brian Bunnnett, University of New Mexico

Cesar Caballero, California State University, San Bernardino

Raechelle Clemmons, California State University, East Bay

Karen Cobbs, University of Central Florida

Stephanie Davis-Kahl, Illinois Wesleyan University

Aimee deChambeau, Stony Brook University

Veronica Diaz, Maricopa Community Colleges

Thomas Dugas, Carnegie Mellon University

Lorraine Frost, California State University, San Bernardino

Kelly Gonzalez, University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center Library

Stacey Greenwell, University of Kentucky

Su Hanfling, University of Sydney

Gregory Heald, University of Northern Colorado

Cathy Hubbs, American University

JoAnn Jacoby, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Margie Jantti, University of Wollongong

Scott Krajewski, Augsburg College

Annette Marksberry, Xavier University

Robert McDonald, Indiana University

Amanda Moore, Hendrix College

Carlos Morales, Lock Haven University of Pennsylvania

Jim Muehlenberg, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Piet Niederhausen, Georgetown University

Audrey Novak, Yale University Library

Mike Osterman, Whitman College

Chris Palazzolo, Emory University

Salvador Rosario, Princeton University

Brian Rosenblum, University of Kansas

Michael Russell, Georgia State University

Marsha Schnirring, Occidental College

Win Shih, University at Albany, State University of New York

Sondra Smith, St. Lawrence University

Zheng Wang, University of California, Los Angeles

David Weinberg-Kinsey, Cardinal Stritch University

Jolee West, Wesleyan University

Holly Willis, University of Southern California, Institute for Multimedia Literacy

Future of Digital Scholarship: Preparation, Training, Curricula

In April 2009, CLIR and Emory University cohosted a two-day symposium, “The Future of Digital Scholarship: Preparation, Training, Curricula.” The symposium brought together experts in digital scholarship—broadly construed as research, publications using digital media, and digital projects—to examine what skills are needed to undertake digital scholarship in the humanities and social sciences. Participants discussed the types of specialized coursework available to prepare students for digital research, additional types of training that would be useful, and whether specialized preparation for digital scholarship provides doctoral graduates with a competitive advantage in seeking tenure-track and other kinds of appointments in academia. A report of the meeting will be made available in 2010.

Frye Leadership Institute

The tenth annual Frye Leadership Institute was held May 31–June 11 at Emory University in Atlanta, Georgia. The institute, which CLIR sponsors with EDUCAUSE and Emory University, was created to develop leaders who can guide and transform academic information services for higher education. To date, the program has trained more than 450 librarians, faculty members, and information technology experts.

Since the Frye Leadership Institute welcomed its first class a decade ago, significant change has occurred in higher education. Advances in technology demand that we reconsider how a library is defined, information technology services are organized, and the college and university are conceptualized. A new academic ecology is emerging that has powerful implications for the organization, discovery, and communication of knowledge. This emerging academic ecology should be reflected in both the substance and the process of the Frye Leadership Institute. In 2010, the Institute will take a year’s hiatus so that the sponsors can develop a vigorous new program for Frye that addresses higher education’s leadership needs in an era of unprecedented change.

A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management

Named in honor of A. R. Zipf, a pioneer in information management systems, this \$10,000 fellowship is awarded annually to a student who is enrolled in graduate school in the early stages of study and shows exceptional promise for leadership and technical achievement in information management. The 2009 recipient was Hollie White, a doctoral student in information science at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. She holds master’s degrees in library and information science from the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign and in English from the University of Georgia. White’s dissertation research focuses on the role that knowledge organization plays in large data and information environments.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Now in its seventh year, the Rovelstad Scholarship provides travel funds for a student of library and information science to attend the annual meeting of the World Library and Information Congress. Katie Henningsen, a master's degree candidate at the Palmer School of Library and Information Science at Long Island University, was the 2009 recipient. The program is supported by funds from Mathilde and Howard Rovelstad.

NEW MODELS

Deep Collaboration

In early 2009, CLIR began to convene meetings with a small group of research library directors who were motivated to experiment with new models of collaboration that could redefine the concept of the research library and produce cost-effective services and programs to better support research and teaching. Topics explored in these meetings have included building campus cyberinfrastructures, developing connections between institutional repositories, collectively negotiating with commercial and external entities in large-scale digitization, cooperative cataloging, participating in academic and research computing roles on campus, and print repository and "insurance" models. As a direct consequence of the meetings, participating universities have submitted to a variety of funding sources grant proposals reflecting the topics under discussion.

A Survey of Digital Humanities Centers in the United States

In November 2008, CLIR published *A Survey of Digital Humanities Centers in the United States*, by Diane M. Zorich. The survey, commissioned as background for the 2008 Scholarly Communications Institute (SCI 6), identified the extent of digital humanities centers—entities where new media and technologies are used for humanities-based research, teaching, and intellectual engagement and experimentation. The report explores the financing, organizational structure, products, services, and sustainability of these centers. It is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub143abst.html>.

CLIR Sponsors' Symposium

On December 10, 2008, CLIR hosted its ninth annual Sponsors' Symposium, titled "Emerging Fields of Study: New Research, Environments, and Credentials." The symposium focused on several aspects of digital humanities scholarship. Presenters described interdisciplinary work that incorporates scientific analysis techniques and objects of medieval studies, explored the impact of technology on traditional disciplinary structures, and considered the issues that arise when old models are discarded. The symposium offered insights into new programs that have been designed to accelerate disciplinary change using new digital resources and tools, and fresh approaches to the training of humanists.

ADVISORY GROUPS

AS OF JUNE 30, 2009

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

Tyrone Cannon
University of San Francisco

Sam Demas
Carleton College

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Lynn Scott Cochrane
Denison University

Connie Vinita Dowell, *Chair*
San Diego State University

Joanne Schneider
Colgate University

A. R. Zipf Fellowship Selection Committee

Miles Efron
University of Texas, Austin

Deanna B. Marcum, *Chair*
Library of Congress

Rena Zipf

Frye Leadership Institute Selection Committee 2009

Alice Bishop
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Cynthia Golden
EDUCAUSE

Frances Maloy
Emory University

Brett Coryell
Emory University

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Diana Oblinger
EDUCAUSE

Hidden Collections Review Panel 2009

Amy Friedlander
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Geneva Henry
Rice University

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Joan Giesecke
University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Michael Keller
Stanford University

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Jacqueline Goldsby
University of Chicago

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Mellon Fellowships Selection Committee 2009

Frederick Colby
University of Oregon

Brenda Foley
Marlboro College

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Amy Friedlander
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Meg Norcia
State University of New York, Brockport

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE JULY 1, 2008–JUNE 30, 2009

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Amistad Research Center New Orleans, LA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Working for Freedom: Documenting Civil Rights Organization"	1/23/09	\$250,000
Avery Research Center for African American History, Charleston, SC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Providing Access to African American Collections at the Avery Research Center"	12/1/08	\$236,920
Alison Babeu (Jones), Medford, MA	To serve as rapporteur at the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/08	\$500
Melissa Baralt, Falls Church, VA	To perform a systematic examination of the results of several of the biggest mass digitization projects affecting materials of interest to scholars	7/16/08	\$4,000
The British Library, London, UK	To support an intern to work on the economic validation and cost modeling of the Preservation Components of the Life Cycle work	11/22/08	\$10,000
California Historical Society San Francisco, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "California Ephemera Project"	12/1/08	247,738
Center for the History of Medicine Boston, MA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Foundations of Public Health Policy"	12/1/08	\$217,933
Paul Courant, Ann Arbor, MI	To write a report on the cost of accessing and storing printed volumes in academic libraries	6/19/08	\$4,000
Gregory Crane, Medford, MA	To support a conference and white paper on language, learning, and communication May 2009	4/1/09	\$3,900
Lori Eakin, Hillsborough, NC	To perform work in support of the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access	1/22/08	\$44,000
Emory University, Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Archives from Atlanta, Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement: the papers of Andrew Young, SCLC, and NAACP-Atlanta, GA"	1/23/09	\$399,172
Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering Archives and Rare Photographs: Two Models for Creating Accession-level Finding Aids Using Archivists' Toolkit"	12/1/08	\$274,889
Goucher College, Baltimore, MD	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Mapping Special Collections for Research and Teaching at Goucher College"	12/1/08	\$198,121
Bernardo Huberman, Palo Alto, CA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/08	\$1,500

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Intelligent Television, New York, NY	To organize panels of professionals from the fields of media, education, and technology for the public opening of the Library of Congress's Culpeper campus	7/8/08	\$45,000
Kanazawa Institute of Technology Library Center, Japan	To host the KIT/CLIR International Roundtable for Library and Information Science	9/1/02	\$15,000
Caroline Levander, Houston, TX	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/08	\$1,500
Library of Congress, Washington, DC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Library of Congress Multi-Sheet Map Series Collection: Africa"	12/1/08	\$240,240
Litchfield Historical Society Litchfield, CT	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Revolutionary Era and Early Republic Holdings"	12/1/08	\$101,209
Shawn Martin, Philadelphia, PA	To convene a meeting on the topic of sustainable open access business models for libraries	11/26/08	\$5,000
Kelly Miller, Charlottesville, VA	To organize and manage the project, "Best Practices for Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives"	12/1/08	\$63,500
Stephen Murray, South Salem, NY	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/08	\$1,500
New York University, New York, NY	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Records of the Communist Party, USA and Library of Reference Center for Marxist Studies"	12/1/08	\$492,901
Northwestern University Library Evanston, IL	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Africana Posters: a collaboration with Northwestern University and Michigan State University"	12/1/08	\$89,733
Douglas Oard, College Park, MD	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/08	\$1,500
Susan Rathbun San Diego Supercomputer Center	To assist the San Diego Supercomputer Center in organizing the Winter 2010 meeting of the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access	5/14/09	\$3,906
Rice University, Houston, TX	To explore the feasibility of establishing a primarily digital library to support the teaching and research needs of a university	12/11/08	\$9,438
Robert W. Woodruff Library Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Processing Voter Education Project Collection"	1/23/09	\$249,461
Katherine Shilton, Los Angeles, CA	To conduct detailed investigations of infrastructure support tool development in the humanities	8/19/08	\$10,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Patricia Soler, Washington, DC	To perform a systematic examination of the results of several of the biggest mass digitization projects affecting materials of interest to scholars	7/16/08	\$4,000
Lisa Spiro, Houston, TX	To perform an analysis of platforms that could be used for the Hidden Collections project	5/7/08	\$5,000
Tim Stinson, Baltimore, MD	To support work on extracting and amplifying DNA found in the leaves of medieval parchment codices at the organism level	9/3/08	\$4,650
Maureen Stone, Woodinville, WA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/08	\$1,500
University of California, Berkeley, Berkeley, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "University and Jepson Herbaria"	12/1/08	\$253,794
University of California, Los Angeles, CA	To support the UCLA Library's undergraduate capstone seminars program	11/7/08	\$10,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Collaboration in Cataloging: Islamic Manuscripts at Michigan"	12/1/08	\$225,931
University of Minnesota	To support a meeting of EthicShare	6/12/08	\$15,000
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Hidden Collections in the Philadelphia Area: A Consortial Processing and Cataloging Initiative"	12/16/08	\$500,000
University of Rochester Rochester, NY	To support Nancy Foster in leading workshops on faculty research behavior	12/4/08	\$9,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2009

**WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a nonprofit organization) as of June 30, 2009, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources' management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2009, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 30 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
September 17, 2009

Members American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2009

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2009</u>
Assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 1,452,070	\$ 457,647	\$ 1,909,717
Investments	-	1,654,254	1,654,254
Accounts receivable	49,061	4,000,000	4,049,061
Furniture and equipment, net	37,648	-	37,648
Other assets	<u>99,591</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>99,591</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,638,370</u>	<u>\$ 6,111,901</u>	<u>\$ 7,750,271</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 243,569	\$ -	\$ 243,569
Accrued expenses	102,423	-	102,423
Due to related entity	<u>397,861</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>397,861</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 743,853</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 743,853</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 894,517</u>	<u>\$ 6,111,901</u>	<u>\$ 7,006,418</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,638,370</u>	<u>\$ 6,111,901</u>	<u>\$ 7,750,271</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2009

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2009</u>
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 143,957	\$ 4,325,530	\$ 4,469,487
Contributions	549,659	-	549,659
Publication sales	5,322	-	5,322
Investment income/(loss)	(142,468)	(76,095)	(218,563)
Other income	<u>199,055</u>	<u>(7,800)</u>	<u>191,255</u>
	<u>\$ 755,525</u>	<u>\$ 4,241,635</u>	<u>\$ 4,997,160</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 4,960,024</u>	<u>\$ (4,960,024)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 5,715,549</u>	<u>\$ (718,389)</u>	<u>\$ 4,997,160</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation	\$ 105,021	\$ -	\$ 105,021
Digital Library	89,915	-	89,915
Leadership	39,544	-	39,544
Other	39,580	-	39,580
Cyberinfrastructure	668,204	-	668,204
The next scholar	<u>4,685,964</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>4,685,964</u>
Total Program services	\$ 5,628,228	\$ -	\$ 5,628,228
Administration	<u>1,313,895</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>1,313,895</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 6,942,123</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 6,942,123</u>
Change in Net Assets	<u>\$ (1,226,574)</u>	<u>\$ (718,389)</u>	<u>\$ (1,944,963)</u>
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 2,121,091</u>	<u>\$ 6,830,290</u>	<u>\$ 8,951,381</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 894,517</u>	<u>\$ 6,111,901</u>	<u>\$ 7,006,418</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2009

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ (1,944,963)
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities	
Depreciation	14,674
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	59,617
Realized (gain) loss on investments	340,125
(Increase) decrease in other assets	(52,346)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	(3,949,107)
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>18,038</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	\$ <u>(5,513,962)</u>
Investing Activities	
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 3,427,354
Purchases of investments	(2,470,397)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(28,497)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	\$ <u>928,460</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ (4,585,502)
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>6,495,219</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	\$ <u>1,909,717</u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information	
Interest paid during the year	\$ _____ -

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council on Library and Information Resources receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsorship revenues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009

(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2009 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

NOTE 2 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 170,515
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(132,867)</u>
	<u>\$ 37,648</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009

(Continued)

NOTE 3- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2009

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ (330,521)	\$ (14,041)	379,758
Bonds	-	(662)	29,519
Corporate fixed income	-	3,436	-
Government securities	8,065	(13,145)	368,075
Certificates of deposit	-	-	589,254
Mutual funds	<u>(17,669)</u>	<u>(35,205)</u>	<u>287,648</u>
Subtotal	<u>\$ (340,125)</u>	<u>\$ (59,617)</u>	<u>\$ 1,654,254</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>\$ 1,710,774</u>
Total	<u>\$ (340,125)</u>	<u>\$ (59,617)</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2009:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 79,542	\$ 101,637	\$ 181,179
Realized gains (losses)	(221,614)	(118,511)	(340,125)
Unrealized gains (losses)	<u>(396)</u>	<u>(59,221)</u>	<u>(59,617)</u>
Total investment return	<u>\$ (142,468)</u>	<u>\$ (76,095)</u>	<u>\$ (218,563)</u>

NOTE 4 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009

(Continued)

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$126,170 in 2009.

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2009, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$1,654,254 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2009 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$1,710,774. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$4,331,000 from one organization which represents 86.67 % of total revenue.

NOTE 8 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, 2009
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 4,025,968
30 - 60 days	15,593
60 - 90 days	-
Over 90 days	7,500
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 4,049,061</u>

NOTE 9 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in February 28, 2010, furthermore, the Council entered into an additional operating lease that commences on March 1, 2010 and expires August 21, 2018, both of these leases are for the same space. The Council on Library

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009

(Continued)

NOTE 9 - Commitments (continued)

and Information Resources subleased part of its space to the Digital Library Federation during the year ending June 30, 2009. Rental expense, net of sublease income for the year ending June 30, 2009 was \$188,824. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in June 1, 2010. Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending June 30, _____	Capital Lease	Operating Leases
2010	\$ 3,588	\$ 233,560
2011	-	258,873
2012	-	267,934
2013	-	277,312
2014	-	1,763,759
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 3,588	\$ <u>2,801,438</u>
Less: Amount representing interest. Present value of net minimum lease payments	(245)	\$ <u>3,343</u>

NOTE 10- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 11 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

A comparison of the carrying value of those financial instruments is as follows:

	Carrying Value	Fair Value
Assets		
Cash and cash equivalents 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 1,909,717	\$ 1,909,717
Investments 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 1,654,254	\$ 1,654,254

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2009
(Concluded)

NOTE 11 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments (continued)

	<u>Carrying Value</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Accounts receivables 6/30/09 Level 2	\$ 4,049,061	\$ 4,049,061
Furniture and equipment, net 6/30/09 Level 2	\$ 37,648	\$ 37,648
Other Assets 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 99,591	\$ 99,591
Liabilities		
Accounts payable 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 243,569	\$ 243,569
Accrued expenses 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 102,423	\$ 102,423
Due to related entity 6/30/09 Level 1	\$ 397,861	\$ 397,861

NOTE 12 - Related Party

The Council on Library and Information Resources shares space with the Digital Library Federation. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for use of space and utilities. The Digital Library Federation paid The Council on Library and Information Resources \$10,868 for the use of space and utilities for the year ended June 30, 2009. The Council on Library and Information Resources has also entered into contracts with clients and has subcontracted with the Digital Library Federation to perform the work. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for any expenses paid by the Council on Library and Information Resources on their behalf.

NOTE 13 - Subsequent Events

The Council on Library and Information Resources will combine with the Digital Library Federation as of July 1, 2009. The Digital Library Federation is a consortium of academic libraries and related organizations that are pioneering the use of electronic-information technologies to extend their collections and services.

The affect of the combination had it been completed prior to the year ending June 30, 2009 would be as follows:

	<u>Prior to Combination</u>	<u>After Combination</u>
Revenue	\$ 4,997,160	\$ 5,780,221
Changes in Net Assets	\$ (1,944,963)	\$(2,489,795)
Unrestricted Net Assets	\$ 894,517	\$ 1,410,915
Temporarily Restricted Net Assets	\$ 6,111,901	\$ 6,111,901

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2009

	The Next Scholar	Cyberinfrastructure	Leadership	Preservation	Digital Library	Other	Total Program Services	Admin.	Total 2009
Employee costs	\$ 164,668	\$ 507,841	\$ 20,871	\$ 43,996	\$ 44,106	\$ 3,909	\$ 785,391	\$ 468,113	\$ 1,253,504
Professional services	4,244,211	49,214	11,688	46,101	14,238	-	4,365,452	172,638	4,538,090
Communications	32,235	74	1,302	-	3,541	1,063	38,215	16,887	55,102
Travel and meetings	234,639	94,107	5,560	12	18,246	33,587	386,151	222,077	608,228
Publications	1,432	16,275	-	14,856	9,325	25	41,913	18,207	60,120
Office operations	8,779	693	123	56	459	996	11,106	415,973	427,079
TOTAL	\$ 4,685,964	\$ 668,204	\$ 39,544	\$ 105,021	\$ 89,915	\$ 39,580	\$ 5,628,228	\$ 1,313,895	\$ 6,942,123

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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